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**A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STP ON
KNOWLEDGE REGARDING SELECTED BEHAVIOURAL DISORDER
IN SCHOOL CHILDREN AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AT
SELECTED PRIMARY SCHOOLS OF JAMUHAR VILLAGES, ROHTAS,
BIHAR.**

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ABSTRACT

Background:- Behavioural disorders among school children are increasing rapidly and may affect emotional, social and academic development. Teachers are often the first persons to identify behavioural changes among children. Structured Teaching Programme (STP) can improve teachers' awareness and management strategies regarding behavioural disorders.

Keywords:- Behavioural disorder, school children, structured teaching programme, knowledge assessment, primary school teachers, Bihar.
Methodology:- A quantitative research approach with pre-experimental one group pre-test post-test design was adopted for the study. A total of 60 primary school teachers were selected using non-probability convenience sampling technique. The study findings revealed significant improvement in post-test knowledge scores after administration of Structured Teaching Programme.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A study to assess the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding selected behavioural disorders in school children among primary school teachers at selected primary schools of Jamuhar villages, Rohtas, Bihar.

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the pre-test level of knowledge regarding behavioural disorders.
- To assess post-test knowledge after administration of STP.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme.
- To find association between knowledge scores and demographic variables.

HYPOTHESIS

- H₁: There is significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge scores.
- H₀: There is no significant association between knowledge scores and demographic variables.

RESEARCH APPROACH

The research approach adopted for the study was quantitative research approach.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design adopted for the study was a pre-experimental one group pre-test post-test design.

- Pre-test was conducted to assess baseline knowledge.
- Structured Teaching Programme was administered.
- Post-test was conducted to evaluate effectiveness of STP.

RESEARCH SETTING

The study was conducted in selected primary schools of Jamuhar villages, Rohtas, Bihar.

POPULATION

The population consisted of all primary school teachers working in selected schools.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLE SIZE

The sample consisted of 60 primary school teachers who fulfilled inclusion criteria.

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SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Non-probability convenience sampling technique was used.

SECTION I: DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	p-value
Age	21–30	20	33.3	0.29
	31–40	25	41.7	
	>40	15	25	
Gender	Male	24	40	0.46
	Female	36	60	

SECTION II: PRE-TEST ASSESSMENT

Knowledge Level	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Inadequate	35	58.3%	15.2
Moderate	20	33.3%	
Adequate	5	8.4%	

Interpretation:- The findings revealed that majority of teachers had inadequate knowledge before administration of Structured Teaching Programme.

SECTION III: POST-TEST ASSESSMENT

Knowledge Level	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Inadequate	5	8.3%	27.8
Moderate	18	30%	
Adequate	37	61.7%	

Interpretation:- Post-test findings demonstrated significant improvement in knowledge after administration of Structured Teaching Programme.

SECTION IV: COMPARISON OF PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST

Variable	Pre-test Mean	Post-test Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
Knowledge Score	15.2	27.8	12.6	8.45	0.001

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Interpretation:- The calculated t-value was significant at $p < 0.05$ level, indicating that Structured Teaching Programme was effective.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings revealed that majority of teachers had inadequate knowledge before intervention. After administration of Structured Teaching Programme, considerable improvement was observed in post-test knowledge scores.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that Structured Teaching Programme was effective in improving knowledge among primary school teachers regarding selected behavioural disorders.

IMPLICATIONS

The study emphasizes the importance of school mental health education and training programmes for teachers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Similar studies can be conducted with larger sample size.
- Comparative studies can be conducted in rural and urban settings.
- Long-term effectiveness can be evaluated.

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